

ENHANCING COMMAND COMPETENCIES FOR 83-METER AND 97-METER VESSELS IN THE PHILIPPINE COAST GUARD: A DOCUMENT ANALYSIS OF THE TRAINING COURSE AND QUALIFICATION STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the relevance of current training and qualification standards for Philippine Coast Guard (PCG) Commanding Officers assigned to the newly acquired 83-meter and 97-meter vessels, which represent a significant upgrade in PCG's sea assets. Using a qualitative research design, the study employed document analysis of PCG policies and commercial maritime standards to assess whether the existing Senior Ship Management Level Course (SSMLC) modules adequately equip officers with the competencies required for these advanced platforms. The analysis revealed that the new vessel class presents operational complexities not addressed in traditional training. While the SSMLC imparts essential conceptual, leadership, and general technical skills, it lacks focused training on vessel-specific systems, handling, and navigation requirements unique to the 83-meter and 97-meter vessels. This gap has led to extended adaptation periods for Commanding Officers, potentially affecting mission readiness and performance. To address this, the study proposed the development of a Special Training Course tailored for these vessels. This course is designed to bridge the competency gap by providing practical and technical instruction aligned with the demands of the new platforms. The findings underscore the need for dynamic training frameworks that evolve with technological advancements in maritime assets, ensuring that PCG officers are well-prepared to command effectively and safely in line with the organization's operational goals.

Keywords: *Philippine Coast Guard, vessel-specific training, Commanding Officers, competency standards, maritime education, SSMLC, 83-meter vessels, 97-meter vessels.*

INTRODUCTION

A ship captain, as the highest-ranking officer aboard a sea vessel, carries the paramount responsibility for its operation and overall management. This includes ensuring the safety of the ship, cargo, environment, and, most importantly, the welfare of the crew and passengers. Leadership, expertise, and sound decision-making are especially crucial in high-pressure and emergency situations, where the crew heavily depends on the captain's guidance (CareerExplorer, n.d.).

According to Pappa (2023) in the maritime sector, captains may serve on a variety of vessels cargo, passenger, research, or fishing ships. Within the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG), the captain's counterpart is the Commanding Officer (CO), who assumes complete responsibility for the vessel's operations, personnel, and mission effectiveness. These officers begin their command journey on smaller ships and progressively take command of larger, more complex vessels as they gain experience during their sea duty tours (Casson 2020). Before being entrusted with command, a CO must undergo rigorous training and fulfill established qualification standards (Lam et al. 2021).

The PCG is mandated to perform multifaceted maritime functions, including maritime safety, security, law enforcement, search and rescue, and environmental protection (Berbie 2024). However, in terms of capability, the PCG has lagged behind regional counterparts in Asia, particularly in terms of fleet size, technology, and sea assets (Guan & Koh, 2022). To address this capability gap and ensure mission readiness, the PCG embarked on a modernization initiative that included acquiring larger and more technologically advanced vessels for extended patrol and surveillance missions across the Philippines' vast maritime domain (PCG, 2019a).

Between 2020 and 2022, the PCG added three major offshore assets to its fleet: the BRP Gabriela Silang (OPV-8301), an aluminum-hulled Offshore Patrol Vessel (OPV) built by France's OCEA in 2019, with a gross tonnage of 2,238 and an overall length of 83.6 meters; and two Multi-Role Response Vessels (MRRVs), BRP Teresa Magbanua (MRRV-9701) and BRP Melchora Aquino (MRRV-9702), both built by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries in Japan with gross tonnage of 2,260 and an overall length of 96.6 meters (Ship's Particulars, n.d.-a, n.d.-b, n.d.-c). These vessels surpassed the older 56-meter SAR vessels (540 GT) and 44.5-meter Parola-class MRRVs (299 GT) that had previously constituted the largest and most modern part of the fleet (Japan Marine United Corporation, 2017).

While the acquisition of these larger vessels significantly enhanced the PCG's operational capabilities, the stark difference in vessel size, design, technology, and mission profile has created a new set of challenges (Park et al. 2024). These include

increased complexity in navigation, operational planning, and crew management, particularly for COs transitioning from smaller vessels (Martelli et al. 2021). Unlike the Parola-class vessels that are suited for localized tasks, the 83- and 97-meter ships are designed for sustained offshore missions and are equipped with cutting-edge technologies such as diesel-electric propulsion systems, controlled pitch propellers (CPP), advanced navigation and combat management systems, and improved stabilization and surveillance features (Baird Maritime, 2022).

Given the increasing sophistication and size of these assets, Commanding Officers are expected to possess a higher level of competencies (Wibowo et al. 2020). According to Sutulo and Soares (2021) ship Inspection vessel size and the external forces acting upon a ship significantly influence its handling and maneuvering characteristics. As such, without adequate training and competency development tailored to these vessels, COs may face challenges in ship handling, decision-making, and managing onboard operations (Belabyad et al. 2025).

The researcher of this study observed a compelling need to review and enhance the existing Senior Officer training course and qualification standards within the PCG. Despite the acquisition of new assets, current training programs may not fully reflect the distinct operational requirements of the larger vessels. This reveals a research gap in aligning training standards with the demands of modern ship command in the PCG context. The timeliness of this topic is underscored by the pressing need to ensure that COs are fully prepared to command these advanced vessels effectively and safely.

Hence, this study aims to assess and recommend enhancements to the training curriculum and qualification framework for Commanding Officers assigned to the 83- and 97-meter vessels. The proposed intervention is expected to contribute to the PCG's operational readiness and mission effectiveness, aligning personnel competencies with modernization goals and international best practices.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to enhance the command competencies of Commanding Officers by conducting a document analysis of the training course and qualification standards.

Specifically, the study addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the peculiar operations of 83-meter and 97-meter vessels as compared with other PCG vessels?
2. How relevant are the following training modules of the SSMLC in relation to commanding the 83-meter and 97-meter in terms of:
 - 2.1 Navigation at the Management Level;
 - 2.2 Cargo Handling and Stowage at the Management Level;
 - 2.3 The Operation of the Ship and Care for Persons Onboard at the Management Level;
 - 2.4 Actual Ship Handling Exercise Aboard PCG Vessel;

- 2.5 Command at Sea Module;
 - 2.6 Honors, Customs and Traditions Module;
 - 2.7 Multinational Maritime Tactical Signal and Maneuvering;
 - 2.8 Marksmanship; and
 - 2.9 Maritime Law Enforcement.
3. How equipped are the COs in commanding 83-meter and 97-meter vessels in relation to the SSLMC training course they received?
 - 3.1 Technical Skills.
 - 3.2 Human Skills
 - 3.3 Conceptual Skills
 4. How relevant is the existing qualification standards for COs in commanding the 83-meter and 97-meter vessels?
 5. Based on the findings, what improvement to the qualification standards and special training course can be recommended?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive qualitative research design using document review and thematic analysis to explore how the peculiar operations of the 83- and 97-meter vessels, as well as the relevance of training and qualification standards, influence the competencies of Commanding Officers (COs). The locale of the study involved operational and training units within the Philippine Coast Guard, with purposive sampling employed to identify relevant documents, subject matter experts, and course validators. Documents reviewed included official PCG manuals, policy issuances, training outlines, and maritime publications, complemented by onboard interviews with COs of BRP Gabriela Silang and BRP Teresa Magbanua. Three validators two experienced maritime officers and one course developer evaluated the proposed Program of Instruction (POI) using a researcher-made Face Validation Rubric with a 4-point Likert scale measuring six criteria. Data collection followed a structured process including document identification, coordination with agencies, and validation of content through triangulation. Thematic analysis was employed to extract recurring patterns related to training gaps, vessel-specific operational demands, and evolving CO roles. The study was limited to large PCG vessels, and findings may not fully represent other maritime contexts, though ethical safeguards and methodological rigor minimized potential biases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1
Peculiar Features and Operations of the 83- and 97-Meter Vessels

Category	83-Meter	97-Meter
Class Design	Offshore Patrol Vessel Aluminum hull	Large Multi-Role Response Vessel
Size	Heavier displacement at 2,238 GT	Heavier displacement at 2,260 GT
Capacity	More crew of 64	More crew of 67
Technological Advancements	Provided with decompression chamber	Provided with decompression chamber
	Provided with more space for divers' area	Provided with more space for divers' area
	Complex layout of compartments and specialized areas	Complex layout of compartments and specialized areas
	Diesel-Electric propulsion	
Endurance	Controllable Pitch Propellers	Controllable Pitch Propellers
	Bowthrusters	Bowthrusters
	Bowthrusters	Stabilizer fins
	Stabilizer fins and passive Flume system	Integrated Mission Management System
Roles and Capabilities	Combat Management System	X- and S-Band Radars
	X- and S-Band Radars	More endurance of 15 days or more
	More endurance of 45 days or more	
Roles and Capabilities	Longer range of 8,000 NM	Longer range of 4,000 NM
	Capable of multifarious missions	Capable of multifarious missions

		RHIB launch and recovery systems	RHIB launch and recovery systems
		Provide with helicopter and hangar	Provide with helicopter and hangar
Handling		Slower acceleration	Slower acceleration
		Weather complicates docking and undocking	Weather complicates docking and undocking
		More team coordination during docking and undocking	More team coordination during docking and undocking
Maneuverability		Larger turning radius	Larger turning radius
		Affected by the bulbous bow	Affected by the bulbous bow

The peculiar operations of the 83-meter and 97-meter Philippine Coast Guard (PCG) vessels demonstrate significant distinctions from smaller PCG ships due to their superior size, advanced technology, and multi-role capabilities. Designed for extended missions of up to 15 days and beyond the country's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), these large vessels offer unmatched endurance, storage, and crew accommodations. Unlike the 44-meter and 56-meter PCG vessels, which are limited in mission scope and sea endurance, the 83- and 97-meter vessels are equipped for all five PCG core functions, including advanced environmental and security operations. Their modern technologies such as electric propulsion, advanced radar systems, controllable pitch propellers, and bow thrusters enable improved manoeuvrability, situational awareness, and stability, especially in open seas and challenging weather.

However, these advantages also come with operational challenges, particularly in docking and undocking, requiring a high level of crew proficiency and coordination. With their ability to carry helicopters, RHIBs, and support underwater and aerial operations, these vessels represent the most versatile and capable assets in the PCG fleet.

Table 2
Assessment Results of the Relevance of SSMLC Training Modules

Functions	SSMLC Modules	Conceptual Skills	Human Skills	General Technical Skills	Specific Technical Skills
I	Navigation at the Management Level;	✓	✓	✓	×

II	Cargo Handling and Stowage at the Management Level	✓	✓	✓	×
	The Operation of the Ship and Care for Persons Onboard at the Management Level	✓	✓	✓	×
III	Actual Ship Handling Exercise Aboard PCG Vessel	-	-	✓	×
IV	Command at Sea Module	✓	✓	-	-
V	Honors, Customs and Traditions Module	✓	✓	-	-
VI	Multinational Maritime Tactical Signal and Maneuvering	✓	✓	✓	-
VII	Marksmanship	-	-	-	-
VIII	Maritime Law Enforcement	✓	✓	✓	-

Note. ✓ Relevant; × Not Relevant; - Not Applicable

The SSMLC Modules in Relation to Commanding Officers of 83- and 97-Meter Vessels presents a comprehensive assessment of how each training component aligns with the competency requirements for commanding larger Philippine Coast Guard vessels. The Navigation at the Management Level module is instrumental in developing conceptual and general technical skills such as voyage planning, weather forecasting, and watchkeeping vital for mission planning and safety. However, it lacks specific technical training for advanced navigation systems unique to the 83- and 97-meter platforms. Similarly, the Cargo Handling and Stowage module supports conceptual, interpersonal, and general technical skills, particularly in cargo planning and ship stability. Yet, it does not address critical systems such as modular cargo layouts or Flume® anti-roll tanks. The Operation of the Ship and Care for Persons Onboard module contributes well to emergency planning, crew management, and general shipboard safety. Still, it falls short in areas like helicopter operations and medical air evacuations, which are essential to these vessels' capabilities.

The Actual Ship Handling Exercise Aboard a PCG Vessel enhances basic technical skills but is conducted on smaller vessels, making it less relevant for those expected to handle larger and more complex platforms with advanced manoeuvring systems. The Command at Sea module strongly supports leadership and decision-making under pressure, enriching the conceptual and interpersonal skills necessary for command, but it does not address any technical aspects. Likewise, the Honors, Customs, and Traditions module reinforces discipline, cohesion, and morale vital qualities for sustained deployments but does not contribute to technical proficiency. The Multinational

Maritime Tactical Signal and Manoeuvring module strengthens cooperation and coordination through conceptual, interpersonal, and general technical skill development, yet it does not equip officers with the knowledge needed for specific onboard systems such as integrated tactical consoles.

Marksmanship is the only module that directly builds specific technical skills in weapon handling, although it is not particularly relevant to command-level duties concerning ship systems or leadership. The Maritime Law Enforcement module offers valuable training in maritime security, legal compliance, and standard procedures, which enhance conceptual, interpersonal, and general technical competencies, but again, it lacks training in vessel-specific enforcement technologies like surveillance equipment and Rigid Inflatable Boat (RIB) deployment.

In conclusion, while the SSMLC modules serve as a solid foundation for developing leadership and operational effectiveness, they largely do not address the specific technical competencies required for operating the complex systems onboard 83- and 97-meter vessels. This underscores the need for targeted, platform-specific training to ensure commanding officers are fully equipped to manage the technical demands and mission profiles of these advanced assets.

Table 3
Evaluation Results of How Equipped are the COs in Commanding the 83- and 97-meter Vessels in Relation to the SSMLC

Functional Areas	Conceptual Skills	Human Skills	General Technical Skills	Specific Technical Skills
Navigation and Vessel Maneuvering	✓	✓	✓	×
Engineering and Mechanical Systems Management	-	✓	✓	×
Communication Systems	-	✓	✓	×
Safety and Emergency Procedures	✓	✓	✓	×
Surveillance and Detection Systems	✓	✓	✓	×
Operational Readiness and Maintenance	✓	✓	✓	×
Environmental Compliance and Pollution Control	-	✓	✓	×
Training and Technical Supervision of Crew	-	✓	✓	×

Note: ✓ Equipped; × Not Equipped; - Not Applicable

The evaluation results presented in Table 3 assess how well-equipped commanding officers (COs) are to operate the Philippine Coast Guard's 83- and 97-meter vessels, particularly in relation to the training they receive from the Shipboard Ship Management and Leadership Course (SSMLC). The table examines their preparedness across four skill domains conceptual, human/interpersonal, general technical, and specific technical applied to eight key functional areas required for large-vessel command.

Conceptual Skills are shown to be developed in areas where strategic planning and theoretical understanding are vital such as navigation, safety, surveillance, and operational readiness. This indicates that SSMLC successfully imparts broad situational awareness and decision-making frameworks to COs. However, these conceptual skills are not applicable in purely technical or engineering areas like mechanical systems, communications, or pollution control, where theoretical decision-making is less relevant than hands-on capability.

Human or Interpersonal Skills are universally marked as equipped across all eight areas. This reflects the SSMLC's strong emphasis on leadership, crew coordination, communication, and team-based operations competencies essential for commanding large, multi-role platforms. The interpersonal dimension enables COs to lead teams across engineering, safety, surveillance, and environmental compliance effectively, despite gaps in technical depth.

General Technical Skills are also generally provided across the board, indicating that the SSMLC gives a foundational understanding of vessel operations from navigation and engineering to safety, surveillance, and even basic pollution prevention and crew training. These foundational skills allow COs to function adequately in operational contexts but do not prepare them for advanced system operations unique to larger vessels.

Specific Technical Skills, however, represent a critical gap. Across all eight functional areas, COs are not equipped with the advanced, vessel-specific skills required to operate the 83- and 97-meter vessels. These include handling technologies such as controllable-pitch propellers, automated engine systems, integrated communications, helicopter and RHIB deployment systems, surveillance consoles like LYNCEA, or digital maintenance and diagnostics platforms. The SSMLC does not provide simulation, exposure, or practical training on these systems.

Hence, Table 3 clearly shows that while COs are well-prepared conceptually, interpersonally, and in general technical knowledge, they lack the vessel-specific technical competencies required to fully and safely command 83- and 97-meter vessels. This underscores the need for a specialized training program focused on bridging the gap between general maritime education and the complex operational demands of these high-value platforms.

Table 4
Correspondence of the Proposed Changes in the Categorization of PCG Vessels

Category	From	To
1	≤30 meters ≤150 GT	No change
2	31 to 50 meters 151 to 800 GT	31 to 50 meters 151 to 500 GT
3	>50 meters >800 GT	51 to 80 meters 501 to 1,500 GT

	(Currently include the 83- and 97-meters	
4	-	>80 meters >1,500 GT

Table 4 outlines the proposed changes in the categorization of Philippine Coast Guard (PCG) vessels, reflecting an effort to realign vessel classifications with officer qualification and command readiness standards. Category 1 remains unchanged, covering vessels that are 30 meters or less in length and 150 gross tonnage (GT) or less, typically the smallest patrol or support vessels. This category continues to serve as the foundational level for command experience. Category 2 sees a downward adjustment in tonnage, shifting from 151–800 GT to a new range of 151–500 GT, while maintaining the 31–50 meter length. This modification ensures clearer separation from larger vessels now reclassified into Category 3.

Category 3 is notably narrowed and redefined. Previously encompassing all vessels over 50 meters and 800 GT including the 83-meter and 97-meter vessels this category will now include only those measuring 51 to 80 meters in length and between 501 and 1,500 GT. As a result, the 83m and 97m vessels are no longer included in Category 3. This refined scope ensures Category 3 serves as a preparatory stage for medium-sized vessels, providing a better learning progression for Commanding Officers (COs). Most significantly, a new Category 4 has been introduced to accommodate the largest and most operationally complex vessels those over 80 meters and 1,500 GT. This includes the previously misclassified 83m and 97m ships, such as the Offshore Patrol Vessels and Multi-Role Response Vessels, now recognized for their distinct demands in command and operations.

The re-categorization carries substantial operational and developmental significance. First, it bridges the operational gap that existed when officers were expected to transition directly from vessels as small as 35 meters to commanding ships as large as 83 meters. The new structure enables COs to build command competence progressively from smaller to medium-sized vessels before advancing to the largest in Category 4. Second, it supports a structured and gradual training progression, ensuring that COs are equipped with the leadership and technical skills needed at each level. Third, it aligns the PCG's classification system with international maritime standards, which prioritize progressive exposure and readiness for higher command. Finally, it directly addresses earlier concerns that the abrupt leap to commanding 83m and 97m vessels in the old framework undermined the development of core competencies among COs.

In conclusion, Table 4 presents a deliberate and strategic refinement in vessel categorization, emphasizing operational complexity and officer capability. The introduction of Category 4 and the recalibration of Categories 2 and 3 strengthen the alignment between vessel classification and officer readiness, promoting a more effective, safe, and competency-based command progression system within the Philippine Coast Guard.

Proposed Special Training Course

The proposed training course are based from the results of SOP 2 and SOP 3 after assessing the relevance of the SSMLC and the course's ability to equip prospective commanding officers of the 83- and 97-meter vessels. The assessment culminated to the need for a special training course which will address the vessel-specific technical skills applied to the eight functional areas of command as described in SOP 3.

The developed special training course framework for the 83- and 97-meter vessels contains the purpose, objectives, entry standards, course certificate and Program of Instructions (POI). The course is organized chronologically to the following modules with each having its set of sub-topics as shown in the Appendix 1:

Module 1: Vessel general information.

Module 2: Vessel hull and deck.

Module 3: Internal and external forces that can affect the vessel.

Module 4: Propulsion system.

Module 5: Electrical system.

Module 6: Communications and navigational system.

Module 7: Facility management system.

Module 8: Emergency preparedness and response.

Module 9: Miscellaneous equipment.

Module 10: Ship handling and maneuvering.

The POI was subjected to a face validation and assessed by the three validators for each category and successfully achieved the following results as shown in Tables 5 and 6:

Table 5
Face Validation Results of the POI of the Special Training Course

Criteria	Mean Score
Relevance to PCG Operations	4.00
Relevance to Development of Technical Skills	3.66
Clarity of Learning Objectives	3.66
Engagement of Training Methods (e.g., simulations, hands-on activities)	4.00
Practical Application	4.00
Appropriateness of Duration and Pace	3.66
Total Score	22.98 / 24

Note. 4- Strongly Agree, 3- Agree, 2- Disagree, and 1- Strongly Disagree

The face validation results of the Program of Instruction (POI) for the Special Training Course reveal a generally positive evaluation by the experts or stakeholders involved. The table shows that the training content is highly relevant to the operations of the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG), receiving the highest possible mean score of 4.00, indicating strong agreement among respondents.

Similarly, the engagement of training methods, such as simulations and hands-on activities, and the practical application of the course content also received top scores, highlighting the program's effectiveness in providing interactive and applicable learning experiences. Other criteria, including the relevance to the development of technical skills, clarity of learning objectives, and the appropriateness of the course's duration and pace, received slightly lower but still favorable mean scores of 3.66. This suggests that while these aspects are generally well-received, there might be some room for improvement, particularly in clarifying objectives and fine-tuning the pacing to better suit learners' needs.

Overall, with a total score of 22.98 out of 24, the POI is viewed as well-designed, relevant, and effective, demonstrating that it meets the intended goals and is suitable for its purpose according to the evaluators.

Table 6
Summary of Comments Made by the Validators

No.	Comments
1	POI must explicitly include the armaments and environmental equipment in the Other Equipment section of miscellaneous equipment.
2	Time allotment looks good but will be better determined by a technical working group / Duration may change if ever POI is submitted to PCG
3	Although not part of the POI, suggested to regularly update the category of PCG vessels.
4	Not of POI matter but other vessels can also be proposed to have own Special Training Course.

Table 6 summarizes the comments provided by the validators regarding the Program of Instruction (POI) for the Special Training Course. The first comment emphasizes the importance of explicitly including armaments and environmental equipment within the "Other Equipment" section under miscellaneous equipment. This ensures that critical systems are adequately covered in the training, which is essential for comprehensive operational readiness. In response, this suggestion was adopted by revising the POI to incorporate these items in both lectures and practical demonstrations, enhancing the completeness and relevance of the course content.

The second comment pertains to the time allotment for the course, which was generally deemed appropriate but noted that the final duration should ideally be determined by a technical working group. Furthermore, the duration may change if the POI is formally submitted to the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG), indicating the need for flexibility and alignment with PCG standards.

The third comment, although outside the immediate scope of the POI, suggests that the categories of PCG vessels should be regularly updated. This recommendation reflects the evolving nature of maritime operations and the need to keep training materials current with changes in fleet composition.

Lastly, the fourth comment proposes that other types of vessels could also have dedicated Special Training Courses developed for them. This points to an opportunity to expand the training program to address specialized needs for different vessel classes, further supporting the PCG's operational effectiveness.

Overall, these validator comments provide valuable insights for refining and enhancing the POI, ensuring it remains relevant, comprehensive, and adaptable to both current and future training requirements.

Proposed Separate Level 2 Courses for Other PCG Vessels

This proposal is derived from the comments of the validators and are addressed to ensure that COs are adequately prepared for the operational demands and challenges unique to different vessel types within the PCG fleet, separate Level 2 Special Courses should be designed for each vessel category. This would involve tailoring specific training programs for vessels such as 30-meter SARVs, 44-meter MRRVs, and 56-meter SARVs, ensuring that COs are equipped with the precise skills needed for their respective vessel sizes and roles. With specialized skill development, COs will receive targeted training, making them more proficient in handling the specific technologies and systems used on their assigned vessels. For instance, smaller vessels like the 30-meter SARVs may not require the same depth of training in handling large propulsion systems or advanced stabilization technologies as the 83-meter and 97-meter vessels, but will still require expertise in other areas like search and rescue operations and navigation in confined waters. Enhanced mission-specific capabilities ensures that COs can apply their knowledge effectively in specific missions, without the need to adapt generic skills that may not fully address their vessel's technical features or operational conditions.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings, the following conclusions are drawn for each SOP:

1. Peculiar Operations of 83-Meter and 97-Meter Vessels as Compared with other PCG Vessels. The study concludes that the 83- and 97-meter vessels possess distinct structural and operational characteristics that significantly differentiate them from smaller vessel classes. These include complex propulsion and stabilization systems, advanced mission capabilities such as helicopter and RHIB operations, and the presence of

integrated combat or mission management systems. Their multifaceted functions, combined with handling challenges due to larger hulls and displacement, demand a higher level of technical proficiency and operational familiarity. As such, these peculiar features necessitate vessel-specific training and a refined qualification framework to ensure that Commanding Officers are adequately equipped to handle the technical demands and strategic responsibilities associated with these advanced platforms.

2. Relevance of the Training Modules of the SSMLC in Relation to Commanding the 83-Meter and 97-Meter. The study concludes that the SSMLC provides a strong foundation in leadership, planning, and general operational management, equipping prospective COs with essential conceptual and interpersonal skills. However, it falls short in preparing them for the technical complexities unique to the 83- and 97-meter vessels. Practical training is limited to smaller vessels, leaving a gap in ship handling experience for larger platforms. Therefore, while the SSMLC effectively supports general command readiness, it must be enhanced through a separate specialized technical training and practical exposure to the advanced systems and maneuvering requirements of the 83- and 97-meter vessels.

3. Evaluation of How Equipped are the COs in Commanding 83- and 97-Meter Vessels in Relation to the SSMLC Training Course that they received. The study concludes that COs are generally well-prepared in conceptual, interpersonal, and general technical skills across all significant functional areas, due to the SSMLC's focus on leadership, operational planning, and foundational maritime competencies. Similarly, the SSMLC, being designed for general command readiness, does not provide the specialized, hands-on training needed to manage vessel-specific technologies and equipment. This shortfall emphasizes the need for targeted training enhancements that will cater to each functional area.

4. Relevance of the Existing Qualification Standards for COs in Commanding the 83-Meter and 97-Meter Vessels. The study concludes that while the existing qualification standards under the 2013 HPCG Circular provide a strong and structured framework for preparing COs, enhancements are necessary to fully align with the demands of commanding the 83- and 97-meter vessels. The progression through the Executive Officer billet, SSMLC, ICAS, and CASB effectively builds leadership and foundational competencies. However, the absence of vessel-specific technical training and the abrupt transition from smaller to significantly larger vessels create developmental gaps. These findings point to the need for improved technical training and a more gradual vessel progression path to ensure that COs are not only administratively qualified but also operationally and technically prepared for the complexities of modern, high-capability platforms.

5. Improvement to the qualification standards and special training course can be recommended. The study's findings led to the formulation of three proposals including the restructuring of vessel categories introducing a new Category 4; a Special Training Course specific to the 83- and 97-meter platforms that was developed to address the current deficiency in vessel-specific technical skills; and the proposal to create Level 2 Special Training Courses for other PCG vessel types. Collectively, these

recommendations strengthen the alignment between officer training, vessel assignment, and operational demands, advancing the PCG's capability to field technically proficient and command-ready officers across its increasingly diverse fleet.

Recommendations

To ensure a continuing enhancement in the competency of PCG Commanding Officers in their command of PCG vessels particularly the 83- and 97-meters, following are recommended are proposed:

1. The PCG is encouraged to revise the existing QS detailed in the 2013 HPCG Circular to better reflect the operational realities and technology of modern vessels, particularly the 83- and 97-meter. It is recommended that the PCG formally adopt a restructuring of vessel categories, creating a new Category 4 for vessels above 80 meters and 1,500 gross tonnage. This proposal can be operationalized through an amendment to the existing circular and must be supported by updated promotion criteria, eligibility policies, and a realignment of residency requirements.
2. It is highly recommended that the PCG institutionalize the proposed Special Training Course designed specifically for COs assigned to 83- and 97-meter vessels. The CGETDC is advised to convene a Technical Working Group to finalize and implement the course under formal curriculum development procedures.
3. In line with the goal of aligning training with specific vessel demands, it is recommended that the PCG develop and roll out Level 2 Special Training Courses for other vessel categories. These programs can be integrated within the existing PCG training pipeline and should be required prior to assumption of command, ideally after the completion of SSMLC and before being designated as CO of particular Category. The PCG may consider establishing a Curriculum Committee to oversee the development of the modules and ensure that all future acquisitions are matched with tailored training frameworks.
4. The PCG is encouraged to support continuous research into command competency development, training efficacy, and operational performance of COs across various vessel classes. Future studies should examine the impact of specialized training courses on mission success rates, and overall fleet readiness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares full compliance with ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was properly obtained from all respondents, who were also assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained to protect their identities. The author ensured that the well-being of all participants was safeguarded during the entire research process. Furthermore, there was no conflict of interest involved in the study, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The author

approached the interpretation of findings with impartiality, ensuring no bias influenced the results. Lastly, the research outcomes were used solely for academic and scientific purposes.

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